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Comment on Raputsoane's Analysis of Regional Differences in Governance of Mining Companies

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Abstract

Raputsoane (2025) analyzes governance standards for mining companies worldwide using a cross-sectional regression to estimate differences between South Africa and the rest of the world. The article starts with S&P Global Ratings' Corporate Sustainability Assessment (CSA) score as a proxy for governance. It compares it to a series of company-specific parameters, including market capitalization, average share price over the prior year, return on equity, return on assets, a variable to reflect required disclosure, and a variable to reflect additional information provided by each company beyond legal requirements. The empirical results show that better governance is correlated with greater disclosure, but other variables do not show a statistically significant correlation with governance. The positive correlation between governance and market cap suggests larger companies are subject to greater scrutiny, but the estimate is not statistically significant. These results lead to valuable discussion about governance outside the mining firm, including government standards.

Keywords: Mining, South Africa, Governance, Fiduciary, S&P Global Ratings, Corporate Sustainability Assessment, Market Capitalization, Return on Equity, Return on Assets, Regression, Cross-Section data, Exploratory Data Analysis, GDP, International Law, International Economics

JEL Codes:

C1 - Econometric and Statistical Methods and Methodology: General

C13 - Estimation: General

D2 - Production and Organizations

D22 - Firm Behaviour: Empirical Analysis

G3 - Corporate Finance and Governance

G32 - Financing Policy ; Financial Risk and Risk Management ; Capital and Ownership Structure ; Value of Firms ; Goodwill (898)

L7 - Industry Studies: Primary Products and Construction

M14 - Corporate Culture ; Diversity ; Social Responsibility

N50 - General, International, or Comparative

O13 - Agriculture ; Natural Resources ; Energy ; Environment ; Other Primary Products

P11 - Planning, Coordination, and Reform

Q32 - Exhaustible Resources and Economic Development

Q33 - Resource Booms

Y1 - Data: Tables and Charts

Y3 - Book Reviews (unclassified)

Comment on Raputsoane's Analysis of Regional Differences in Governance of Mining Companies

Raputsoane (2025) analyzes governance for mining companies worldwide using a cross-sectional regression that includes a dummy variable to test for differences in governance levels between South Africa and the rest of the world. The article starts with S&P Global Ratings' Corporate Sustainability Assessment (CSA) score as a proxy for governance. It compares it to a series of company-specific parameters, including market capitalization, average share price over the prior year, return on equity, return on assets, a variable to reflect required disclosure, and a variable to reflect additional information provided by each company beyond legal requirements. The empirical results show that better governance is correlated with greater disclosure, but other variables do not show a statistically significant correlation with governance. The positive correlation between governance and market cap is interesting, as larger companies are subject to greater scrutiny, but the estimate is not statistically significant.

The Q-Q plot of residuals in Appendix 2 of Raputsoane (2025) shows that the model captures some of the data's variation, but not all of it. Is linear regression missing some variation because the data is non-linear? For example, the market cap variable has fat tails; it may be better to use a transformed version of the data, such as the square root of market capitalization. I would also like to see more exploratory data analysis, similar to Figure 1. For example, how does the scatterplot of governance score versus market capitalization for all firms compare with the scatterplot of governance score versus the square root of market capitalization?

The linear regression equation used by Raputsoane (2025) tests for a change in the average level of governance between South Africa and the rest of the world, after controlling for the dependent variables. The categorical variable or dummy variable (D) only affects the average level of the dependent variable (Y) governance, but is it possible that there are interaction effects between location (D) and things like share price (X)? For example, governance for larger companies differs in South America compared to other places, so we need to use a dummy variable to capture a change in the slope coefficient between X and D? These interaction effects

could be associated with the new standards from the Institute of Directors South Africa mentioned by Raputsoane (2025).

In addition, can we expand this analysis to consider a time-series dimension? The cross-sectional basis is a good start, and it may provide more insight when used in a panel model over time. And what about survivorship bias among companies?

An essential consideration in the mining business is that it has high capital intensity. It is possible to expand Raputsoane's (2025) regression equation by considering the role of debt in governance outcomes. Capital assets for mining companies can be funded by debt when the company generates a positive return on assets, and mining companies can have very high levels of indebtedness. Do governance standards of mining companies differ between companies that are more heavily in debt versus others? Does governance relate to the indebtedness of a mining firm? Does the "return on assets" for a mining company have any relationship to the financing decisions for the capital structure in terms of the total amount of capital for the company and the proportions of debt and equity financing? Can we connect this line of investigation to Raputsoane's (2025) test of how return on assets is correlated with governance? There are significant variations in the amounts and types of capital available to mining companies over time, and these variations provide opportunities to use exploratory data analysis to generate new theoretical insights or test existing theoretical predictions about mining companies.

Exploratory data analysis helps identify patterns in data that reflect stylized assumptions from a toy model of a mining company. It helps develop statistics or ratios to compare mining companies of all sizes worldwide. For example, can we test the hypothesis that companies with the most significant additional disclosure values also have the most debt financing? It may help to measure debt financing in terms of the debt/equity ratio for each mining company separately to adjust for company size when comparing data on a cross-sectional basis. Do the mining companies with the most debt leverage share other common statistical features? Raputsoane (2025) shows how to combine several different types of data; can we push it further to include larger data sets with non-numerical data fields that can be explored using statistical methods for cluster analysis on a cross-sectional basis?

It is also possible to compare the capital structures of mining companies with those of other types of companies, such as oil companies. There are significant differences in the economics of oil and metal resource extraction, with substantial differences in capital and operating costs across project lifecycles. These differences can be summarized in the adage, “*When you drill oil, your problems are over. When you drill copper, your problems are just beginning.*” A new oil well has significant up-front capital costs to establish production capabilities. Still, it can have relatively low sustaining capital costs and extremely low operating costs for primary oil production, under stylized assumptions for a basic oil well. The reality of the modern oil industry is complicated by vertical integration across production, processing, distribution, corporate ownership, and government involvement.

Mining companies around the world face similar competitive pressures for vertical integration driven by economies of scale, and it may be interesting to compare the oil and mining industries in terms of industry consolidation. It is possible to use the Gini Coefficient as a statistical measure of industry consolidation and compare different parts of the mining and oil business over time. This modelling framework can be used to investigate further how the local legal framework in one country affects mining and oil industry statistics over time. What can we learn from the countries with the strongest growth rates compared to their corporate governance standards, for example? These ideas can guide an investigation using exploratory data analysis to expand on Raputsoane’s (2025) article.

There are essential governance questions for mining exploration companies. Still, they are outside the scope of this article because exploration companies have no revenue and are not rated by S&P Global for its Corporate Sustainability Assessment. Also, mining exploration companies do not use debt until they are into the development phase of building a new mine (if at all). This pattern of equity-funded mining exploration companies differs from the business model of pharmaceutical research companies, which are also pre-revenue and similar to mining exploration companies. In contrast, pharmaceutical research companies typically have significant debt, unlike mining exploration companies. This is a rich area of research, with examples such as the Golec and Vernon (2007) paper titled “Financial Risk in the Biotechnology Industry” and the Thakor and Lo (2017) paper titled “Optimal Financing for R&D-Intensive

Firms.” It is helpful to explore how mining companies fit into these other research frameworks, both in terms of theoretical models of the incentives for mining companies and of the empirical data on the structure of individual mining companies and parts of the global mining industry.

For further comparison, technology research companies vary widely: some pre-revenue companies have substantial debt, while others do not. The niche-market ecosystem for ultra-high-risk research companies across various industries determines the amount of capital available, the cost of capital, and the relative composition of debt and equity. Can we compare governance standards across multiple industries, such as mining, pharmaceuticals, and technology? Can we compare governance standards across companies at different lifecycle stages within each sector?

Raputsoane (2025) mentions how South Africa recently implemented a “distinctive set of corporate governance practices” through the Institute of Directors South Africa, and I wonder whether this could serve as a policy template for other countries? For comparison, Australia has a coordinated framework for corporate law between all types of corporate entities and levels of government. Canada's legal framework is complicated because inter-provincial differences cause significant trade distortions within the country. For example, BC has a “luxury tax” on Albertans who own certain types of real estate in BC. For another example, Alberta is unable to build pipelines to transport oil products at the rate they would like because the province of BC is involved. The Canadian legal framework separates Provincial and Federal responsibilities, making it difficult to coordinate policy across various levels of government. Government policy in Canada is a complicated patchwork of competing regulatory rules.

Canadian capital markets are provincially regulated, but the federal government is always watching. Government decisions are now affecting company decisions. For example, SolGold PLC provides a complex case study of a company that left Canadian jurisdiction for Switzerland and the London Stock Exchange! Also, the use of the Investment Canada Act (ICA) to prohibit Shandong Gold Mining Co., Ltd. from acquiring Canadian gold producer TMAC Resources Inc. presents another example of how the government makes dynamic legal decisions in the mining business. Mining companies face a complex regulatory framework in Canada, whether they do

business domestically or abroad.

Furthermore, there are important legal events that continue to occur in Canada regarding mining. For example, the case of Nevsun Resources Ltd. reached the Supreme Court of Canada in 2020, where nine judges ruled and decided to dismiss the appeal, with four judges dissenting in whole or in part. Appeal to overturn the decision by the BC Supreme Court that allows a lawsuit to be heard in Canada against a Canadian mining company for human rights abuses against workers at a mine it owned in Eritrea. These court decisions set important precedents in Canada and the international community. The political leadership in Canada may follow the lead from the courts on this topic and create a new policy that further consolidates the spirit of the law as interpreted by the judges in these various decisions. In fact, I believe the international community is watching these court decisions and waiting for the Canadian government to show policy leadership as a broader part of efforts towards truth and reconciliation. I think the court's decisions are in line with the type of policy that supernational economic entities want to see from countries going forward. There are many opportunities to improve on the impacts of the mining industry, and governance plays an important role.

Consider how the sovereign wealth fund called the Government Pension Fund of Norway, or *Statens pensjonsfond*, uses its ethical committee to provide oversight to its investment management professionals. This institution is an important case study for many reasons. There are relevant questions in public economics, like how do royalties and other taxes on oil production compare between Norway and other countries over time? How much government spending did Norway have to give up when it started the fund, and how did this change the government's spending? There are relevant questions for international economics, like whether the fund can lead countries to new policies to clarify liabilities for mining companies that operate abroad. The scenarios where the fund makes public decisions to divest of specific businesses based on ethical criteria have all been "negative," where a company has not met minimum standards for their business fundamentals. Imagine if the fund starts to talk publicly about investments it makes based on "positive" ethical criteria, such as mining companies where the waste rock removes carbon from the atmosphere? The modern framework

of global financial markets provides new ways to coordinate incentives between counterparties.

Another example of an important case study is the pending foreign takeover of Teck Resources Ltd. The federal government requires corporate headquarters to remain in Canada, but the company announced it would abandon its Canadian stock listing as part of the deal (McGee, 2025)! Does uncertainty about the government's rules make it more difficult for Directors to fulfill their fiduciary duties or achieve higher governance ratings? Company governance depends on the legal framework, and the Canadian government makes decisions on a case-by-case basis for major things like corporate takeovers. I think the government has opportunities to improve its governance standards through greater transparency and standardization. For example, how exactly does the federal government perform the net benefit test under the Investment Canada Act? I think it would be useful to provide a few examples of relevant calculations for global audiences to better understand Canadian policy dynamics.

Why does the federal government want Teck Resources to keep its headquarters in Canada? A large number of people in Canada are affected by Teck's activities, and the government needs to be able to interact with the company. The company claims it contributed almost USD \$25 billion towards global GDP in 2022, with approximately half in Canada and 10% each in the USA, Chile, and Peru (Teck Resources Ltd, 2022). This is an example of Teck Resources providing leadership in the mining industry globally by presenting statistical information that is comparable to government data. Teck could provide a very detailed breakdown of their economic activity globally in a way that goes beyond their required disclosure and represents "additional disclosure" in the model of Raputsoane (2025), whose results show that additional disclosure does have a positive correlation to governance values. It is useful to see an actual example of "additional disclosure" from a Canadian mining company! It would be interesting to see if the Canadian government could partner with Teck Resources to further study the data that Teck uses to estimate their global GDP contribution. This could give the data teams at Statistics Canada exposure to new ideas from industry and improve disclosure standards overall for companies and government. Coordinate data fields to help make comparisons more consistent between sources of data over time.

Teck Resources' current market capitalization is around USD \$19 billion. Suppose Teck becomes a foreign company; could this significantly affect the Canadian government's ability to interact with Teck in terms of records kept outside Canada or the ability to enforce legal action? The mining industry globally is changing as we see more spending by governments to support individual projects or groups of projects through regional infrastructure. You can't move an orebody, but you can move a corporate headquarters! It's also worthwhile to note that countries like Mexico or the Democratic Republic of Congo have different legal frameworks than Canada for the way that companies can do mining in the country. The Canadian government can improve its policy planning by studying the way mining is taxed everywhere around the world and bringing new ideas to Canada for different ways to structure the economic and legal fundamentals of the mining industry.

It may seem like a small part of the negotiation to keep Teck Resources' corporate headquarters in Canada. Still, it is meaningful as a single negotiating point for the federal government. Why does the government of Canada prioritize keeping its headquarters in the country? I believe there can be a "loss of information" when a Canadian company sells to a foreign owner. This is like bankruptcy because of non-monetary effects in Bernanke (1983), except that a foreign takeover is like bankruptcy. Loss of information for the mining community is a significant problem because it is costly to replicate the valuable information on the research and development of mines in an area. Is there a relationship between the corporate governance values in Raputsoane (2025) and the types of mining companies that ever get a takeover offer? Can we further consider the GDP contributions of these companies that are takeover targets compared with other mining companies that don't get takeover offers? Are there historical scenarios where local mining industries were taken over by outsiders and then profits declined subsequently to show an empirical example of the costs of this lost information value in terms of lower GDP?

References

Bernanke, B. (1983), “*Irreversibility, Uncertainty, and Cyclical Investment,*” The Quarterly Journal of Economics, Vol. 98, No. 1, pp. 85-106

Golec, J.H., Vernon, J.A. (2007), “*Financial Risk in the Biotechnology Industry,*” NBER Working Papers 13604, National Bureau of Economic Research, Inc.

McGee, N. (2025), “Carney told Anglo American to move headquarters to Canada for Teck deal approval, sources say,” The Globe and Mail, accessed on November 17, 2025:
<https://www.theglobeandmail.com/business/article-teck-resources-anglo-american-mark-carney-mining-deal/>

Raputsoane, L. (2025), “*Global mineral companies' attributes and corporate governance,*” MPRA Paper #123205, <https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/id/eprint/123205>

Teck Resources Ltd. (2022), “2022 Economic Contribution Report,” Accessed on November 17, 2025:
<https://www.teck.com/sustainability/sustainability-topics/communities-and-indigenous-peoples/economic-contributions/#:~:text=2022%20Economic%20Contributions%20Report%20%2D%20English.to%20governments%20across%20the%20world>

Thakor, R.T., and Lo, A.W. (2017) “*Optimal Financing for R&D-Intensive Firms,*” NBER Working Papers 23831, National Bureau of Economic Research, Inc.

Supreme Court of Canada, (2020), “Supreme Court Judgments: Nevsun Resources Ltd. v. Araya,” Accessed on November 17, 2025:
<https://decisions.scc-csc.ca/scc-csc/scc-csc/en/item/18169/index.do>